

Studies in Temperature Coefficients of some Photochemical Reactions in various Solvents in Dark and in Light.

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Dhar and his co-workers (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1926, **32**, 586) have carried out a systematic study of temperature coefficients of a number of chemical reactions both photochemical and thermal.

In 1923 Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1923, **128**, 218) put forward the view that the temperature coefficient decreases with the increase in the order of reaction, that is, it is

- (1) highest in case of zero-molecular,
- (2) lower for unimolecular, and
- (3) lowest for multimolecular reactions.

However the experimental data quoted by Dhar and his co-worker in support of this theory are probably not quite sufficient to justify a generalisation of this kind (also *cf.* von Halban, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **67**, 129).

The von Halban-Dhar rule on account of the recent theories of catalysis and chemical reactions deserves a thorough investigation particularly with respect to the effect of the solvent on various reactants. It is also important to compare in every case the temperature coefficient of reactions both in the light and in the dark.

The present investigation was undertaken with the above mentioned points in view.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following reactions were studied :—

(a) The oxidation of hydrogen sulphide by means of oxygen (in excess) in presence and in absence of light.

(b) Bromination of lactic acid in different solvents in dark and in presence of light (electric bulb 1,500 c. p.).

(c) Bromination of cinnamic acid in different solvents in absence and in presence of light.

Oxidation of Hydrogen Sulphide.

Salazar and Newman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, *ii*, 64, 66) found the evidence of slight oxidation on keeping the solution of hydrogen sulphide in air. The aqueous solution is called "hydrogen sulphide water." The solution is supposed to contain H° and HS' and S'' ions but the ionisation, $H_2S \rightarrow H^{\circ} + HS'$ is relatively much greater than $H_2S \rightarrow 2H^{\circ} + S''$.

Dilute solutions of hydrogen sulphide were prepared in distilled water. The reaction vessel used was a big boiling tube. As a result of a number of preliminary experiments it was noticed that the reaction is to a certain extent influenced by the catalytic effect of the walls of the vessel and that the reaction could best be studied by using an ordinary boiling tube. The tube was placed in a thermostat, the temperature of which was maintained constant within $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

It was found necessary to regulate the flow of oxygen. The proper flow of the gas was arrived at after a series of trials. The rate of reaction was measured iodometrically by taking out 5 c. c. of the solution from the reaction mixture at definite intervals of time.

TABLE I.

Oxidation of H₂S (2H₂S + O₂ = 2H₂O + 2S).

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature 40°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of H ₂ S in c. c. of N/10-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. <i>k</i> = 0.4348 <i>K</i> .	Time in minutes.	Concentration of H ₂ S in c. c. of N/10-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. <i>k</i> = 0.4348 <i>K</i> .	Time in minutes.	Concentration of H ₂ S in c. c. of N/10-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. <i>k</i> = 0.4348 <i>K</i> .	
0	2.30	—	0	2.02	—	0	2.07	—	
5	1.80	0.0212	5	1.62	0.0190	6	1.82	0.0150	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20}$
10	1.30	0.0243	10	1.28	0.0198	10	1.48	0.0161	= 0.869
16	1.00	0.0226	16	1.02	0.0197	15	1.22	0.0140	$\frac{Kt+40}{Kt+30}$
20	0.75	0.0211	20	0.80	0.0191	20	0.74	„	= 0.856
Mean	0.0223		27	0.60	0.0198	35	0.50	0.0170	
			Mean	0.0194		Mean	0.0160		
<i>Dark.</i>									
0	2.10	—	0	2.40	—	0	2.05	—	
5	2.00	0.0042	5	2.15	0.0095	5	1.75	0.0137	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20}$
10	1.90	0.0048	10	2.05	0.0068	10	1.65	0.0091	= 1.37
15	1.80	0.0044	18	1.80	0.0069	13	1.55	0.0098	$\frac{Kt+40}{Kt+30}$
24	1.65	„	23	1.68	0.0068	20	1.35	0.0091	= 1.5
Mean	0.0044		Mean	0.0067		Mean	0.0092		

The temperature above 40° could not be tried as there was an appreciable loss of sulphuretted hydrogen even in dilute solutions at temperatures higher than 40°. The velocity constants were irregular and hence rejected.

Bromination of Lactic Acid.

Bromine reacts with lactic acid in light to give pyruvic acid according to the equation:

The reaction has also been worked out by Ghosh and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 38) with the object of finding out how the velocity constant of photo-bromination varies with intensity, frequency and state of polarisation of incident light.

The rate of reaction was measured iodometrically as before. The light source was a 1,500 c. p. bulb placed at a distance of 12 cm. from the reaction vessel.

TABLE II.

*Bromine (N/50) and Lactic Acid (N/50).**Solvent—Water.*

Temperature 15°.			Temperature 25°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c. c. of N/100.Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K$.	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c. c. of N/100.Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K$.	
0	3.8	—	0	2.9	—	
5	3.4	0.0097	20	2.0	0.0080	
15	3.0	0.0069	25	1.9	0.0071	$\frac{Kt+25}{Kt+15} = 1.16$
20	2.8	0.0066	30	1.65	0.0080	
25	2.6	0.0062	35	1.6	0.0072	$\frac{Kt+35}{Kt+25} = 1.24$
30	2.3	0.0069	40	1.4	0.0080	
35	2.2	0.0068	45	1.2	0.0083	
	Mean	0.0066		Mean	0.0077	
Temperature 35°.			Temperature 45°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c. c. of N/100.Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K$.	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c. c. of N/100.Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K$.	
0	3.8	—	0	2.6	—	
5	3.4	0.0098	10	2.0	0.0114	
10	3.2	0.0100	15	1.7	0.0114	
15	3.0	0.0091	20	1.5	0.0123	$\frac{Kt+45}{Kt+35} = 1.19$
20	2.8	0.0095	25	1.4	0.0110	
25	2.4	0.0093	30	1.2	0.0112	
30	2.2	0.0093	35	1.1	0.0110	
	Mean	0.0095		Mean	0.0114	

TABLE III.

*Bromine (N/50) and Lactic Acid (N/50.)**Solvent—Water.*

Temperature 15°.			Temperature 25°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant. $k = 0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant $k = 0.4343K.$	
0	3.9	—	0	3.1	—	$\frac{Kt + 25}{Kt + 15} = 1.0$
5	3.7	0.0045	5	3.0	(0.0023)	
15	3.3	0.0044	10	2.8	0.0044	
22	3.1	0.0041	15	2.6	0.0043	
32	2.8	0.0042	35	2.2	0.0042	
Mean 0.0043			Mean 0.0043			
Temperature 35°.			Temperature 45°.			$\frac{Kt + 45}{Kt + 35} = 1.8$
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant. $k = 0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant $k = 0.4343K.$	
0	4.45	—	0	3.4	—	
5	4.15	(0.0060)	5	3.0	(0.0108)	
10	4.05	0.0042	10	2.8	0.0084	
15	3.75	0.0044	14	2.6	0.0079	
20	3.50	0.0047	17	2.5	0.0079	
25	3.35	0.0046	22	2.1	0.0081	
30	3.25	0.0047	Mean 0.0080			
35	3.15	0.0048	Mean 0.0045			

Results in the Dark.

The results in the dark are rather interesting. It would be clear from Table III (reaction velocity at 15°, 25° and 35° respectively) that velocity constant is same and does not increase with the rise in temperature. But the reaction proceeds with a greater velocity at 45°. Here the velocity is nearly double. The value of the temperature coefficient is 1.8.

Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1925, 2, 39) has also tried this reaction at 35° (dark). The velocity of reaction as found by him is much less than found here. We are unable to explain the difference although we have carefully repeated our results a number of times.

It may be mentioned that a bimolecular reaction velocity equation was tried but was not found to give as good a constant as the

monomolecular equation excepting in case of the reaction at 35° (dark), where the bimolecular equation also gave a fairly satisfactory constant.

TABLE IV.

Solvent—Chloroform.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K.$	
0	5.2	—	0	3.00	—	
10	1.6	0.0511	7	0.90	0.0740	
13	1.2	0.0490	10	0.70	0.0630	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 1.35$
17	0.7	0.0510	12	0.10	0.0654	
20	0.4	0.0510	14	0.25	0.0720	
	Mean	0.0504	21	0.10	0.0700	
				Mean	0.0700	
<i>Dark.</i>						
Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K.$	
0	0.60	—	0	0.80	—	
29	0.55	0.0013	13	0.70	0.0044	
60	0.50	0.0013	29	0.65	0.0031	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 2.35$
74	0.48	0.0013	50	0.55	0.0032	
87	0.45	0.0013	69	0.48	0.0032	
	Mean	0.0013		Mean	0.0034	

TABLE V.

Solvent—Carbon tetrachloride.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			
<i>Light.</i>						
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant, $k = 0.4943K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Velocity constant, $k = 0.4943K.$	Temperature coefficient.
0	2.20	—	0	6.6	—	
7	2.00	0.0059	34	3.5	0.0081	
12	1.90	0.0053	48	2.5	0.0087	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 1.5$
20	1.70	0.0056	60	2.0	0.0086	
46	1.20	0.0057				
		Mean 0.0055			Mean 0.0084	

Dark.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			
0	2.25	—	0	2.0	—	
15	2.15	0.0013	14	1.80	0.0085	
23	2.10	0.0013	22	1.70	0.0082	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 2.54$
50	1.90	0.0014	70	1.20	0.0081	
		Mean 0.0013	76	1.15	0.0084	
					Mean 0.0083	

TABLE VI.

Temperature Coefficients of the Reaction between Lactic acid and Bromine in different Solvents, Concentration N/50 each.

<i>Light.</i>		<i>Dark.</i>	
Solvent.	Temperature coefficient.	Solvent.	Temperature coefficient.
	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20}$		$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20}$
Carbon tetrachloride	... 1.50	Carbon tetrachloride	... 2.58
Chloroform	... 1.35	Chloroform	... 2.35
Water	.. 1.20	Water	... 1.80

The reaction was tried in carbon disulphide in light and in dark but it did not work.

Reaction between Bromine and Cinnamic Acid.

The reaction between bromine and cinnamic acid has been worked by Mathur, Gupta and Bhatnagar at one temperature (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1928, 2, 243).

Ghose and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 261) have also studied this reaction in plane polarised, circularly polarised and ordinary light. The reaction proceeds fairly quickly in light but in dark the velocity is slow.

The velocity measurements were similarly carried on. The solvents tried were carbon disulphide, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate, ethyl bromide and ethyl formate.

It was found that in the dark the reaction is irregular in the beginning and also there is period of inhibition. So the two solutions of bromine and cinnamic acid after mixing were allowed to stand for half an hour and then the reaction velocity was measured.

Merck's pure bromine was used. Solutions of bromine and cinnamic acid were separately prepared in different solvents. Equimolecular solutions of both the reactants were used but it was found that reaction works according to unimolecular equations.

It may also be mentioned that Sudborough and Thomas (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 245C) have studied the reaction between equimolecular solutions of bromine and cinnamic acid in carbon tetrachloride at 15° in day light. They consider the reaction to be bimolecular but the values of the constant as calculated by them by the bimolecular equation vary from 4.33×10^{-2} to 7.18×10^{-2} . Very much better constancy in the values can be obtained when their results are recalculated by the help of the unimolecular equation as shown below:—

$$a = 26.15$$

t (hrs.).	$(a-x)$.	$\frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$.	* $\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0.5	16.7	4.33×10^{-2}	0.389
1.0	12.7	4.05×10^{-2}	0.316
1.5	8.15	5.63×10^{-2}	0.337
2.0	5.5	7.18×10^{-2}	0.338

It is, therefore, evident that they were not justified in considering the reaction to be bimolecular.

* Sudborough and Thomas, *loc. cit.*

TABLE VII.
Bromination of Cinnamic Acid in Carbon Disulphide.
 Bromine = N/30. Cinnamic acid = N/30.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	
0	1.65	—	0	2.00	—	
10	0.95	0.0239	4	1.50	0.0301	
20	0.80	0.0157	8	1.10	0.0324	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 1.98$
28	0.60	0.0157	16	0.70	0.0304	
37	0.45	0.0152	27	0.300	0.0300	
	Mean	0.0155		Mean	0.0305	
Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	
0	1.60	—	0	1.60	—	
10	1.40	0.0058	8	1.20	0.0156	
20	1.80	0.0045	15	0.90	0.0166	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 3.75$
29	1.20	0.0042	23	0.65	0.0177	
30	1.05	0.0048	50	0.30	0.0165	
	Mean	0.0046		Mean	0.0164	

TABLE VIII.
Bromination of Cinnamic acid in Carbon Tetrachloride.
 Bromine = N/30. Cinnamic acid = N/30.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature 40°.			Temperature coefficient.
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K$	
0	3.45	—	0	2.20	—	0	3.50	—	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 1.8$
9	2.70	0.0118	20	0.90	0.025	16	0.80	0.0405	
16	2.20	0.0122	34	0.55	0.022	22	0.48	0.0401	$\frac{Kt+40}{Kt+30} = 1.8$
23	1.55	0.0151	46	0.32	0.020	27	0.20	0.0420	
32	1.25	0.0130	53	0.15	0.024	37	0.10	0.0410	
40	1.00	0.0130							
61	0.70	0.0110		Mean	0.0227		Mean	0.0409	
	Mean	0.0126							

Dark.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K.$	
0	4.00	—	0	2.60	—	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 3.6$
30	3.60	0.0015	34	2.45	0.0047	
45	3.40	0.0015	40	2.30	0.0048	
60	3.35	0.0013	47	2.10	0.0050	
75	3.30	0.0013	54	1.95	0.0049	
Mean	0.0014		Mean	0.0049		

TABLE IX.

Bromination of Cinnamic Acid in Chloroform.

Bromine = N/30. Cinnamic acid = N/30.

Light.

Temperature 20°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature 40°.			
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/500 Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100 Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.4345K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100 Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant. $k=0.1343K.$	Temp. coefficient.
0	4.80	—	0	5.00	—	0	4.40	—	
14	4.60	0.0013	20	4.40	0.0027	21	3.55	0.0044	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 1.72$
24	4.50	0.0012	33	4.10	0.0026	32	3.20	0.0043	$\frac{Kt+40}{Kt+30} = 1.72$
43	4.05	0.0017	45	3.75	0.0027	62	2.40	0.0042	
51	3.95	0.0016	62	3.55	0.0024	Mean	0.0043		
Mean	0.0015		70	3.35	Mean 0.0026				

Dark.

Temperature 26°.			Temperature 30°.			Temperature coefficient
Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/500 Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4343K.$	Time in minutes.	Concentration of Br ₂ in c.c. of N/100 Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	Velocity constant $k=0.4345K.$	
0	3.60	—	0	2.40	—	$\frac{Kt+30}{Kt+20} = 3.5$
22	3.50	0.00056	39	2.00	0.0020	
46	3.40	0.00054	57	1.90	0.0019	
86	3.20	0.00059	62	1.82	0.0020	
Mean	0.00056		80	1.75	0.0020	
Mean	0.00056		Mean	0.0019		

TABLE X.

Reaction in Light.

Reactants.	Solvent.	Dielectric constant.	Temperature.	Velocity constant.	Temperature coefficient.
Lactic acid and bromine.	Water.	81	15°	0·0066	1·15
			25°	0·0077	1·24
			35°	0·0095	1·19
			45°	0·0114	
	Chloroform.	5·14	20°	0·0504	1·35
			30°	0·0700	
Carbon tetra-chloride.	2·25	20°	0·0055	1·50	
		30°	0·0084		
Cinnamic acid and bromine.	Chloroform.	5·14	20°	0·0015	1·72
			30°	0·0026	1·72
			40°	0·0043	
	Carbon tetra-chloride.	2·25	20°	0·0126	1·81
			30°	0·0227	1·82
			40°	0·0410	
Carbon disul-phide.	2·61	20°	0·0155	1·98	
		30°	0·0300		

TABLE XI.

Reaction in Dark.

Reactants.	Solvents.	Dielectric constant.	Temperature.	Velocity constant.	Temperature coefficient.
Bromine and lactic acid.	Water.	81	15°	0·0043	1·80
			25°	0·0043	
			35°	0·0045	
			45°	0·0080	
	Chloroform.	5·14	20°	0·0013	2·61
			30°	0·0034	
Carbon tetra-chloride.	2·25	20°	0·0013	2·54	
		30°	0·0033		
Bromine and cinnamic acid.	Chloroform.	5·14	20°	0·0005	3·50
			30°	0·0019	
	Carbon tetra-chloride.	2·25	20°	0·0013	3·60
			30°	0·0048	
	Carbon disul-phide.	2·61	20°	0·0045	3·75
			30°	0·0165	

TABLE XII.

*Bromination of Cinnamic Acid and Lactic Acid.**Relation between Velocity Constant and Dielectric Constant.*

Solvent.	Dielectric constant.	Velocity constant at 20°.	
		Lactic acid.	Cinnamic acid.
Carbon tetrachloride.	2.25	0.0500	0.0014
Carbon disulphide.	2.61	—	0.0431
Chloroform.	5.14	0.0095	0.0190
Water.	81.00	0.0066	Not tried.

From the above table it is clear that there can be no possibility of any relationship between the dielectric constant and velocity constant.

These results are in agreement with the results of Mathur, Gupta and Bhatnagar (*loc. cit.*) on the bromination of cinnamic acid in various media. These are further supported by the work of Oliver (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1916, **36**, 117) on acid chlorides of benzene sulphonic acid derivatives in various solvents and also by Matthew and Williamson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2577) who have observed that the isomeric change of acetyl chloraminobenzene into *p*-chloracetanilide under the influence of ultra-violet rays is more rapid in ethyl alcohol than either in benzene or acetic acid, but the dielectric constant increases in the order:—

Benzene : Acetic acid : Alcohol.

The halogen acetic acids are decomposed by light (Enter, *Ber.*, 1915, **49**, 1366) more rapidly in ether than in benzene but the dielectric constant of benzene is lower than that of ether.

The changes of certain leuco-derivatives of the triphenyl methane series under the influence of ultra-violet rays were studied by Lifschitz and Joffe (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, **97**, 426). They have observed the reaction to proceed more rapidly in ethyl alcohol than in ether or benzene and here again the dielectric constant of alcohol is much higher than either of ether or benzene.

From the above it is clear that there exists no direct relationship between the velocity constant and dielectric constant.

In the following table the temperature coefficients and the dielectric constant of the solvents have been assembled together.

TABLE XIII.

Relation between Temperature Coefficient and Dielectric Constant.

Solvent.	Dielectric constant.	Bromination of cinnamic acid.		Bromination of lactic acid.	
		<i>Light.</i>	<i>Dark.</i>	<i>Light.</i>	<i>Dark.</i>
Carbon tetrachloride.	2.25	1.80	3.60	1.50	2.58
Carbon disulphide.	2.61	1.98	3.75	...	...
Chloroform.	5.14	1.72	3.50	1.45	2.35
Water.	81	...	...	1.20	1.80

Bromination of Cinnamic Acid.

From the above tables it is clear that the solvents can be arranged as follows according to the values of temperature coefficient as obtained experimentally:—

Carbon disulphide: Carbon tetrachloride: Chloroform.

Taking into consideration the influence of dielectric constant the order should be:—

Carbon tetrachloride: Carbon disulphide: Chloroform.

Thus it is seen that the order of the temperature coefficient found experimentally does not show any relationship with the dielectric constant.

Similarly in the case of investigations on the bromination of lactic acid no definite relationship between the temperature coefficients and the dielectric constants of the media is found to hold good.

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